

ELIXIR Commissioned Service DATAREX WP2

D2.1 Overview of ELIXIR services for management of research outputs

Tier: Technology

Priority Area: T1, N4, P1

Thematic Area (if applicable): Research Data Management

Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.1 “Overview of ELIXIR services for the management of research outputs” documents the work of DATAREX task T2.1 to “define, provide, and maintain an overview of the ELIXIR services for management of research outputs and define relevant use cases or user stories, including resources and stakeholder engagements”. Concretely, this task built on previous work, including the outputs from ELIXIR Biohackathon projects and ELIXIR All Hands workshops, to generate accessible and user friendly representations documenting the complex ecosystem of research data management resources within ELIXIR. Through a combination of online and in-person activities, a series of representative user stories and frequently asked questions encountered by research data management professionals were shaped and refined into a new guidelines page on the ELIXIR website.

The utility and success of the new guidelines are indisputable, with usage statistics indicating hundreds of views since their publication. The work successfully improved ecosystem accessibility, coordinated RDM knowledge, and ensured maintenance. While content expanded significantly, the ecosystem structure remained largely unchanged, adding only the Data Stewardship Handbook—highlighting the substantial investment needed for new resources, typically driven by major initiatives like ELIXIR Converge and IMI FAIRplus. The work also highlighted the ELIXIR Toolkit Theme as vital for the development of new resources, suggesting that strengthening its support through funding or in-kind contributions would provide high value for ELIXIR and the wider research community.

Document info

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CDR	Core Data Resource
EDD	ELIXIR Deposition Database
ETT	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme
FAQ	Frequently Asked Question
RDM	Research Data Management
RIR	Recommended Interoperability Resource

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Introduction - the ELIXIR RDM ecosystem

In the scope of this work and in alignment with the ELIXIR Interoperability Platform, the ELIXIR Research Data Management (RDM) ecosystem was defined as the collection of ELIXIR resources that end users might use in combination or alone to address RDM tasks. These include:

- RDMkit (<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>)
- FAIR Cookbook (<https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/>)
- Data Stewardship Wizard (<https://ds-wizard.org/>)
- FAIRsharing (<https://fairsharing.org/>)
- TeSS (<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>)
- bio.tools (<https://bio.tools/>)
- Data Stewardship Handbook (<https://elixir-europe.github.io/ds-handbook/>)

The guidance provided by these resources facilitates the use of the ELIXIR Data Deposition Databases (EDDs) and the ELIXIR Core Data Resources (CDRs), as well as guidance on leveraging supported resources such as the ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resources (RIRs).

Representation of the RDM ecosystem

As part of the work of DATAREX task T2.1, the RDM community has created an overview of the ecosystem, its interconnection and illustrated possible user journeys across the resources. The users journeys along with a catalogue of frequently asked questions is available through the ELIXIR main website and in a separate document on Zenodo.

User journeys and FAQs

The first draft of the user journeys was generated through a project at the 2022 ELIXIR Biohackathon¹. The first version was refined and expanded to include the RDM Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) during workshops at the 2023 and 2024 ELIXIR All Hands meetings, as well as an online workshop organised as part of the DATAREX WP2 milestone M2.2 in two online events a workshops 31.01.2024 and a contentathon 25./26.06.2024. Following these workshops, the journeys and FAQs underwent another round of review by the RDM Community before being published as a standalone document on Zenodo² and as part of the "Guidelines" section of the ELIXIR website, under <https://elixir-europe.org/what-we-offer/guidelines/data-management>.

¹ https://osf.io/preprints/biohackrxiv/emc2f_v1

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14710085>

The Zenodo version of the user journeys has been viewed 563 times at the time of submission of this document, with 430 recorded downloads of the PDF document. The guidelines also had 758 unique visits on the ELIXIR website at the time of writing.

The publication of the guidelines on the ELIXIR website highlighted a major challenge in how ELIXIR communities can, or rather cannot, provide input on the public representation of information in their area of expertise. The guidelines, although validated extensively in terms of content by experts from the RDM Community, had to undergo further review prior to their inclusion in the ELIXIR website. This led to repeated delays compared to the originally targeted publication deadline of Q3-2024, with publication finally taking place in April 2025. The ELIXIR guidelines page also underwent changes from the version published in Zenodo and that were not validated by the RDM Community, such as the use of different versions of the user journey representations.

The challenges encountered during the publication process raise additional concerns regarding the maintainability of these guidelines. Since ELIXIR Communities operate with no or very limited funding, the time and resources available to regularly review and update materials are also limited, and any roadblocks to these review efforts jeopardise the successful implementation of improvements and corrections. The impact of these challenges is indirectly illustrated by the recent proliferation of new resources created by ELIXIR Communities and Platforms that are based on the ELIXIR Toolkit Theme³ (ETT), a framework designed for the easy deployment of documentation websites.

Other representations

In addition to the primary overview of the RDM ecosystem created during DATAREX, work from this task also contributed to the Interoperability Platform's Guide to the Portfolio of FAIR-enabling Services⁴, which includes many of the same resources. The guide was created as part of the Interoperability Platform programme of work 2024-2026 and includes contributions from a range of sources, including the RDM Community and DATAREX.

Outcomes and expected impact

Although the DATAREX project plan did not include a formal "Expected Outcomes and Impacts" section, the intended outcomes of task T2.1 were to make it easier for the

³ <https://elixir-belgium.github.io/elixir-toolkit-theme/>

⁴ https://elixir-europe.github.io/interoperability_2024-26/portfolio

research community to utilise the ecosystem, to coordinate RDM knowledge in the ecosystem and to ensure its maintenance.

All of these outcomes were achieved successfully, with the representation presented above providing a cohesive overview of the ecosystem to make all its component resources and their connections more accessible to the research community. Through tasks T2.1 and T2.2, and in collaboration with the ELIXIR Interoperability Platform, we coordinated RDM knowledge content across various resources in the ecosystem and ensured its continuous expansion and maintenance to keep it relevant and fit for purpose. This in turn allowed us to continue promoting, and facilitating the adoption of best practices in RDM and FAIR training, as evidenced for example by the access numbers for the RDM user journeys and FAQs.

It is noteworthy that while the evolution of the content of the various ecosystem resources during the course of DATAREX, presented in the related deliverable D2.2, has been substantial, the ecosystem itself has remained relatively static, with only the addition of one new resource, the Data Stewardship Handbook. This highlights that not only do the existing resources cover the RDM space well but also the amount of investment required, in terms of time and funding, to get new platforms or resources off the ground. While the creation of new content can be achieved through many smaller contributions from enthusiastic experts, either through direct outreach or dedicated events such as contentathons, the development of resources is usually only feasible through major projects such as ELIXIR Converge and IMI FAIRplus, which gave rise to the RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook, respectively.

The ELIXIR Toolkit Theme (ETT) mentioned above can function as an enabler here, serving for example as the starting point for the new DS Handbook. The ETT itself however suffers from capacity limitations, with currently only one dedicated developer supporting its maintenance. Increasing the ETT's resilience and sustainability through a more distributed support system, either from dedicated funding or from in-kind contributions from Nodes and Communities whose resources benefit from the existence of the ETT, would therefore constitute a high return on investment for the whole of ELIXIR and the wider research community.

Dissemination Plans

This deliverable will be uploaded to Zenodo within the ELIXIR Zenodo Community.⁵ Separate dissemination activities and plans exist for the individual resources that are

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/elixir>

part of the ecosystem, as well as in the ongoing activities of the RDM Community. No dedicated dissemination plans exist for the representation of the ecosystem.